

Grit, Social Support, and Psychological Distress in Early Adulthood Indonesian with Divorced Parents

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Abstract

Parental divorce has a negative impact in the form of psychological distress on their children. This impact not only occurs during childhood, but also into their adulthood. This study aims to examine the role of grit and social support on psychological distress. The participants of this study were 161 individuals in Indonesia with divorced parents and in the age range of 21-40 years. This research design is cross-sectional and non-experimental. Data collection used Grit-S questionnaire, Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS), and Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K10). Multiple linear regression analysis was used to test the hypothesis. The results of this study are grit and social support can predict psychological distress, but the role of social support is greater than grit.

Keywords: *Early adulthood, grit, parental divorce, psychological distress, social support*

1. Introduction

The divorce rate in Indonesia has been increasing over time. In 2020, 291,677 divorce cases were reported, and this number rose by 53.5% in 2021. Comparing 2021 and 2022, divorce cases increased by 15.31%. From 2016 to 2022, the number of divorce cases in Indonesia reached 516,334 in 2022, the highest in the last six years (Biro Pusat Statistik Indonesia, 2023, as cited in Kompas.com, 2023).

The impact of divorce on married couples does not end with them; it extends to their children. The negative consequences of parental divorce significantly affect children not only during their childhood but also into adulthood (Amato, 1994; Liana & Suryadi, 2018). In Indonesia, an individual is categorized as an early adulthood from 21 to 40 years old. This period is a transitional phase in cognitive, social, and physical aspects, characterized by developmental tasks such as identity formation, independence, and intimacy with a partner (Santrock, 2012). However, parental divorce increases the risk of individuals experiencing stress, depression, anxiety, substance abuse (smoking, alcohol, drugs), suicidal thoughts, and even suicide attempts (Aursperg et al., 2019).

Parental divorce is a significant life event for a child and can be categorized as traumatic. Psychological distress is one of the adverse psychological effects experienced by children of divorced parents (Størksen et al., 2007). Children caught in the middle of parental conflict can experience psychological distress, characterized by symptoms of depression and anxiety. These symptoms may manifest psychologically, such as feelings of unhappiness, loss of interest, or physically, such as body tension, restlessness, headaches, lack of energy,

insomnia, and more (Belay et al., 2021). According to the APA (2013), psychological distress is defined as a collection of symptoms of depression, anxiety, and undifferentiated functional disorders, characterized by disturbing and confusing personality traits and behavioral issues.

Parental divorce places children at the center of their parents' conflict, leading to loyalty conflicts. Interparental conflict during divorce is the most significant stressor as children struggle to adjust to their parents' separation (Reynolds et al., 2014). When children are forced to take sides, they may feel guilt and shame for rejecting or betraying one parent, resulting in losing support from the rejected parent (Amato & Afifi, 2006). These children may also feel responsible for repairing their parents' relationship and act as mediators (Shimkowski & Ledbetter, 2018). Parents engrossed in their problems may neglect their children's psychological and physical well-being, exacerbating the stress children feel.

Grit is one factor influencing psychological distress. Grit is defined as perseverance and passion for long-term goals (Duckworth et al., 2007). Grit consists of two dimensions: perseverance of effort, referring to the extent to which individuals overcome challenges while maintaining effort and determination for long-term goals, and consistency of interest, describing the extent to which individuals stay focused on achieving their primary long-term goals.

Previous studies have discussed the relationship between grit and psychological distress. Peng & Wu (2022) found that grit serves as a protective factor against psychological distress. Increasing grit can help prevent and reduce psychological distress levels. Grit is also described as a positive personal trait for coping with stress and tackling problems (Stoffel & Cain, 2018). Individuals with high grit are associated with lower levels of depression, stress, anxiety, and anxiety sensitivity (Datu, 2021). Hu et al. (2023) also found that grit mediates the relationship between religious belief and pandemic-induced psychological distress.

Another factor influencing psychological distress is social support. Perceived social support refers to an individual's perception of receiving assistance, whether psychological, material, or holistic, from family, friends, and other sources when needed (Ioannou et al., 2019). Studies have shown that high perceived social support correlates with lower psychological distress levels (Aliyah & Kusdiyati, 2021; del-Pino-Casado et al., 2022; Kathiwada et al., 2021). However, limited research explores the relationship between social support and psychological distress in individuals with divorced parents.

This research studying the relationship between grit with psychological distress and social support. Grit has also been extensively discussed with social support in academic contexts (Salim et al., 2023; Clark et al., 2019; Datu et al., 2017), Covid-19 (Hou et al., 2021), entrepreneurial commitment (Sulu & Purba, 2022), and more. However, no prior studies have explored grit, social support, and psychological distress in a single study. Furthermore, no research has examined these three variables in participants with divorced parents. Therefore, this study hypothesizes that grit and social support are negatively correlated with psychological distress in early adulthood individuals with divorced parents.

2. Research Methods

Participants

The participants of this study were 161 early adulthood individuals with divorced parents. The questionnaire was distributed online using the snowball method via the researcher's social media accounts from December 16, 2023, to January 8, 2024.

The questionnaire included informed consent forms, participant identity section, and scales for each variable. The inclusion criteria for participants, mentioned in the introduction section, were: (1) male or female individuals aged 21 to 40 years old, and (2) having divorced parents.

Design

This study is a quantitative, non-experimental study. The research design employed is cross-sectional.

Instruments

Psychological Distress: In this study, psychological distress was measured using the Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K10) by Kessler (2003), translated and adapted by Tran et al. (2019). The scale consists of 10 items. An example of an item is, "In the last 4 weeks, how often have you felt nervous?" The response categories range from "Never" to "Always," with a score range of 1-5 and reliability $\alpha = 0.895$.

Grit: Grit was measured using the Grit-S scale by Duckworth & Quinn (2009), translated and adapted by Rizal (2022). This scale consists of 8 items. An example of an item is, "When I get a new task, my attention sometimes gets diverted." The response categories range from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree," with a score range of 1-5 and reliability $\alpha = 0.906$.

Social Support: Social support was measured using the Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support by Zimet et al. (1988), translated and adapted by Winahayu et al. (2015). This scale consists of 12 items. An example of an item is, "I can talk about my problems with my friends." The response categories range from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree," with a score range of 1-7 and reliability $\alpha = 0.782$.

Data Analysis Technique

The data analysis technique used in this study was multiple linear regression analysis.

3. Research Results

The demographic data in Table 1 shows that 84.47% of the respondents are in the age category of 21 to 25 years old (136 individuals). The majority of respondents have parents who have been divorced for 11 to 20 years (44.72%, 72 individuals), followed by those whose parents have been divorced for 1 to 10 years (40.99%, 66 individuals), and 21 to 30 years (14.29%, 23 individuals). Most respondents reside on the island of Java (70.81%, 114 individuals), with Sumatra being the second most domicile resided (18.01%, 29 individuals). The majority of respondents live with their mothers (50.31%, 81 individuals), followed by

those living alone (26.71%, 43 individuals), with grandparents (6.83%, 11 individuals), with fathers (6.21%, 10 individuals), and other arrangements.

Regarding occupation, the respondents are primarily students (43.48%, 70 individuals), employees in privately-owned companies (24.84%, 40 individuals), or unemployed (16.77%, 27 individuals), with several other occupational categories represented.

The hypothesis results in Table 2 indicate that grit and social support predict psychological distress in early adulthood individuals with divorced parents ($R^2 = 0.194$; $F = 18.980$; $p < 0.001$). Social support contributes more to predicting psychological distress ($\beta = -0.300$, $p < 0.001$) compared to grit ($\beta = -0.261$, $p < 0.001$).

Table 1.
Demographic Data

No.	Demographic	Details	Number (f)	Percentage (%)
1.	Gender	Women	145	90.06
		Men	16	9.94
		TOTAL	161	100
2.	Age (years)	21 – 25	136	84.47
		26 – 30	21	13.04
		31 – 35	3	1.86
		36 - 40	1	0.62
		TOTAL	161	100
3.	Duration Parents Divorced (years)	11-20	72	44.72
		1-10	66	40.99
		21-30	23	14.29
		TOTAL	161	100
4.	Domicile	Java	114	70.81
		Sumatra	29	18.01
		Sulawesi	10	6.21
		Kalimantan	6	3.73
		Bali	1	0.62
		Nusa Tenggara Barat	1	0.62
		TOTAL	161	100
5.	Currently Living With	Mom	81	50.31
		Alone	43	26.71
		Grandfather &/or Grandmother	11	6.83
		Father	10	6.21
		Sibling	7	4.35
		Husband/ Wife/ Partner	5	3.11
		Parent's sibling (uncle/ aunt)	2	1.24
		Adoptive parents	1	0.62
		Both parents	1	0.62
		TOTAL	161	100
		6.	Occupation	Student
Employee in Privately Owned Companies	40			24.84
Not Employed	27			16.77
Freelancer	7			4.35
Lecturer/Teacher	6			3.73
Self-employed	4			2.48
Housewife	3			1.86
Civil Servant	3			1.86
Nun	1			0.62
TOTAL	161			100

Table 2.
Hypothesis Test Result

No.	Variabel	R ²	F	β	Sig.
1.	Grit and Social Support with Psychological Distress	.194	18.980	-	.001
2.	Grit	-	-	-.261	.001
3.	Social Support	-	-	-.300	.001

4. Discussion

This study found that grit and social support could predict psychological distress in early adulthood individuals with divorced parents. Previous research has shown that individuals with grit negatively correlate with stress, anxiety, depression, and suicidal ideation (Datu, 2021; Kleiman et al., 2013; Stoffel & Cain, 2018). This is because the higher the level of grit, the more individuals exhibit positive behaviors and psychological traits, which in turn reduce psychological distress (Liu et al., 2022). Individuals with grit focus on their long-term goals, and grit is demonstrated in psychological traits or behaviors such as positive hope, optimism, perseverance, pride, self-efficacy, and good self-regulation (Alhadabi & Karpinski, 2020; O’Neal et al., 2016; Sheridan et al., 2015; Singh & Jha, 2008; Wolters & Hussain, 2014).

These positive psychological traits and behaviors enable individuals to exhibit positive coping mechanisms, helping them deal with situations that cause stress, distress, or depression. In other words, grit, as a positive psychological trait, helps individuals maintain good psychological conditions and adapt to changes in their lives (Beasley et al., 2003; Vainio & Daukantaitė, 2016). Individuals with grit view negative life experiences, such as parental divorce, as just one part of life’s broader experiences.

The study also revealed that social support is a stronger predictor of psychological distress than grit. This can be explained by the fact that emotions influence the way cognition functions, especially during the experience of parental divorce. Emotions affect perception, attention, reasoning, memory, and problem-solving (Thyng et al., 2017). Emotional processing by the amygdala and cognitive processing by the hippocampus are not separate processes but are highly integrated, mediating and modulating each other (Dolcos et al., 2011; Okon-Singer et al., 2015). In other words, emotions can significantly modify an individual's cognitive appraisal and memory processing abilities, and vice versa.

Moreover, emotional processing by the amygdala enhances memory consolidation within the memory network. When processing negative emotions, the amygdala activates the frontal and parietal areas that regulate attention focus (Tyng et al., 2017). Emotional experiences trigger the release of stress hormones like adrenaline and activate β-noradrenergic receptors in the basolateral complex of the amygdala (BLA), which then release epinephrine and glucocorticoids in the BLA, consolidating memories with emotional content (Rooszendaal & McGaugh, 2002). This demonstrates that amygdala activation influences the release of hormones and neurotransmitters related to stress, enhancing the consolidation of emotionally charged memories. Thus, it can be concluded that the stronger an individual's emotional charge for an event, the more vividly they will remember the memory.

Humans tend to focus on negative information and stimuli, a phenomenon known as the negativity bias. This bias is innate and serves as an adaptive function for survival, enabling humans to detect, respond to, or avoid negative stimuli. On the one hand, individuals are responsive to perceived threats. On the other hand, they take a longer time to process and respond to negative stimuli, a phenomenon known as negative delay (Kauschke et al., 2019). Therefore, individuals who face negative experiences may take a long time to process those experiences, shift their attention to other things, and detach themselves from the negative event.

The explanations regarding emotions, memory processing, and negativity bias clarify why grit, an internal factor, has a lower predictive value for psychological distress than social support, an external factor. This is because individuals focus on negative stimuli, in this case, the event of parental divorce, rather than seeking solutions or resolving the issue. Even individuals with high grit may find their attention locked onto the negative experience of parental divorce. Thus, social support is needed to help them navigate these difficult times.

The role of supportive people are crucial in helping these individuals move past their issues and find ways to address them. Social support can come from family members or non-family sources, such as friends, peer groups, or online communities. Social support systems, which are forms of coping, are divided into two types: instrumental support and emotional support (Taylor & Friedman, 2011). Instrumental support includes providing information, goods, or services, while emotional support involves offering emotional comfort through validation and positive affirmations. This study aligns with previous research, which shows that perceived social support reduces psychological distress (Aliyah & Kusdiyati, 2021), negatively correlates with stress and adjustment problems (Wolchik et al., 1989), and positively correlates with quality-of-life evaluations (Sorek, 2020).

5. Conclusion

This study found that grit and social support could predict psychological distress conditions. However, external factors like social support play a more significant role than internal factors like grit in predicting psychological distress in early adulthood individuals with divorced parents. This can occur because emotions influence individuals' attention, cognition, and problem-solving abilities. Therefore, external assistance in the form of social support is necessary to help individuals cope with their problems.

Future researchers are encouraged to explore grit, social support, and psychological distress using qualitative methods. They may also delve deeper into the emotional and cognitive processing systems of individuals with divorced parents.

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